

Assessment of Digital Marketing Skills Acquired for Digital Marketing Activities Among Business Education Students in Universities in Bayelsa State

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DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17238722>

Abstract

This study assessed the digital marketing skills acquired for digital marketing activities among Business Education students in universities in Bayelsa State. Two research questions guided the study and two null hypotheses were tested at 0.05 level of significance. The study adopted the descriptive survey research design. The population for the study was 274 respondents which comprised 98 male and 176 female Business Education final year students in Universities in Bayelsa State. There was no sampling because the population was manageable. The instrument used for data collection was a 13-item structured questionnaire titled “Digital Marketing Skills acquired for Digital Marketing Activities Questionnaire (DMSADMAQ)”. The instrument was validated by three research experts. To ascertain the internal consistency of the instrument, Cronbach Alpha method was used to collect data from a trial test. The computation yielded .79 and .80 for clusters 1 and 2 respectively. The instrument had an overall reliability index of .80 which indicated that the instrument was reliable. The research questions were answered using mean and standard deviation while the hypotheses were tested with t-test statistic. The findings of the study showed that social media marketing skills and content marketing skills are acquired by Business Education students for digital marketing activities in universities in Bayelsa State. In line with the findings, the researcher recommended among others that Universities in Bayelsa State should integrate comprehensive digital marketing courses into the Business Education curriculum, with a focus on enhancing social media and content marketing skills.

Keywords: Digital Marketing Skills, Business Education Students, Digital Marketing Activities and Bayelsa State Universities

Introduction

Business education is a specialized discipline focused on imparting essential business knowledge and skills to students through vocational programs across different academic levels. It involves various teaching strategies aimed at providing students with a foundational understanding of business operations and principles. The primary goal of business education is to equip students with the necessary tools to start and successfully manage small businesses. In addition to entrepreneurship, business education offers a diverse range of subjects, including accounting, economics, marketing, and management, ensuring that students are well-rounded in their understanding of business practices. Nwokike (2017) and Ordu (2020) both agreed that the Business Education programme offers a comprehensive curriculum, covering various business courses such as Business Administration, Marketing, Accounting, Purchasing and Supply, Business Studies, Office Information Management, Entrepreneurship, and Distribution. Furthermore, business education plays a crucial role in developing practical skills such as word processing, computer literacy, and office technology management, which are indispensable in

today's business environment. The curriculum is designed to address both theoretical concepts and hands-on training to prepare students for real-world challenges. Business education is not limited to traditional classroom settings but also integrates modern tools and techniques, enhancing students' ability to adapt to technological advancements (Nwokike, 2017). Students are trained in essential business disciplines that can be directly applied in the workforce or in their entrepreneurial ventures. The versatility of business education also allows students to pursue various career paths, from corporate management to starting their own businesses. Business education equips individuals with essential entrepreneurial and managerial knowledge, enabling them to effectively promote businesses through digital marketing skills.

Digital marketing has emerged as a critical aspect of modern business strategies, especially in the era of technological advancement and the global interconnectedness of markets. Digital skills are defined as a range of abilities to use digital devices, communication applications, and networks to access and manage information. Digital skills go beyond the ability to just use devices. It extend to production, selection, evaluation, sharing, and using digital devices, such as computers and smartphones as well as relevant applications. Chaouchi and Bourgeau (2020) noted that some digital skills are required to use and interact with technology in order to fulfill specific tasks, while others are required to design, create and maintain tools and solutions for different industries. The rapid growth of Internet access and connectivity has been attributed to the development of a digital economy across the world. Agwazie and Ordu (2023) posited that the integration of digital skills technology in teaching is a crucial matter in ensuring quality of business education courses. Digital literacy is an essential prerequisite for achieving competence in digital marketing, particularly among Business Education students. It encompasses the ability to use digital tools effectively, including navigating the internet, understanding social media platforms, and managing digital content (Akpotohwo, 2017).

Digital marketing has become increasingly important for universities, particularly during the pandemic, as it provides a platform for institutions to engage with potential students and stakeholders. With many people now turning to the internet for information, search engines like Google, Yahoo, and Amazon have become primary tools for discovering educational opportunities. One of the most effective strategies in digital marketing is maximizing Search Engine Optimization (SEO), as it offers a cost-effective and efficient way to enhance a university's online presence. Research by eMarketer highlights that the education sector is among the leading industries that must embrace social media as a core component of their digital marketing efforts. The use of social media in education has numerous benefits, such as creating a space for students and educators to interact in a more dynamic and accessible way. Furthermore, advancements in technology, particularly the internet, have revolutionized communication, making it faster, more affordable, and more effective. Computer-Mediated Communication (CMC) has played a crucial role in facilitating remote learning, offering a wide range of tools for communication, collaboration, and knowledge sharing. As universities continue to adapt to the digital age, leveraging these digital marketing strategies will be essential for reaching a broader audience and staying competitive in a rapidly changing environment.

In Nigeria, the growing prevalence of digital literacy and the increasing penetration of the internet have underscored the importance of these skills for businesses seeking to remain competitive in a globalized market (Onyeagoro & Uche, 2021). Social media platforms such as Facebook, Instagram, and Twitter have become essential tools for Nigerian marketers, enabling them to connect with a broad and diverse audience, drive customer engagement, and foster brand

loyalty (Nwachukwu et al., 2023). Additionally, the ability to analyze digital marketing metrics is vital for making data-driven decisions, which is critical for optimizing the effectiveness of marketing campaigns (Ibrahim, 2020). The digital economy in Nigeria continues to grow, and as a result, the demand for professionals with expertise in digital marketing is expected to rise significantly in the coming years (Chukwu & Okafor, 2022). This growing demand highlights the need for individuals and businesses to invest in acquiring these skills to ensure success in an increasingly competitive and technology-driven market. In particular, businesses looking to expand their reach and influence must harness the power of digital marketing to stay relevant and attract customers. As more Nigerian entrepreneurs and organizations recognize the potential of digital marketing, there is a growing emphasis on training and upskilling in these areas. For both individuals and businesses, developing digital marketing proficiency is no longer optional but a necessity to thrive in the fast-evolving global marketplace. Digital marketing skills are crucial for navigating the modern business environment, as they involve leveraging online platforms and tools to effectively promote products, services, or ideas. Key skills in this area include search engine optimization (SEO), social media marketing, email marketing, content creation, and data analytics (Eze et al., 2022). Meanwhile, this study focused on social media marketing skills and content creation marketing skills.

Social media marketing skills involve creating, curating, and sharing engaging content to attract and retain an online audience. They include expertise in content creation, audience targeting, analytics interpretation, and social media advertising. Strong communication, creativity, and adaptability are essential for responding to trends and audience preferences (Eze et al., 2022). Mastering these skills helps businesses and individuals increase brand awareness, drive traffic, and boost customer engagement. Social media marketing skills and content creation marketing skills are closely connected, as high-quality, engaging content is essential for attracting and retaining audiences in content creation marketing skills.

Content creation marketing skills involve developing valuable, relevant, and engaging content to attract and retain a target audience. These skills include writing, graphic design, video production, and storytelling to enhance brand messaging. Strong research abilities help in understanding audience needs and creating content that resonates with them. SEO (Search Engine Optimization) skills are essential for improving content visibility on search engines (Joe, 2013). Consistency and adaptability are crucial for maintaining audience engagement and responding to changing trends. Mastering these skills helps businesses build brand authority, generate leads, and drive conversions. Content creation marketing skills are influenced by communication styles, audience engagement strategies, and platform preferences, all of which are shaped by gender.

Gender refers to the social and cultural distinctions associated with being male or female, influencing roles, behaviours, and opportunities in various fields. In the assessment of digital marketing skills acquired for digital marketing activities among business education students in universities in Bayelsa State, gender plays a crucial role in shaping students' access to training, technological adaptability, and confidence in utilizing digital tools. Therefore, understanding gender differences in digital marketing skills acquisition is essential for designing inclusive educational strategies that enhance equal participation and competence among all students. It is based on the above background that the present study assessed digital marketing skills acquired for digital marketing activities among business education students in universities in Bayelsa State.

Statement of Problem

The rapid evolution of digital marketing has necessitated the acquisition of relevant digital marketing skills among business education students to enhance their employability and entrepreneurial capabilities. However, there is a growing concern that business education students in universities in Bayelsa State may not be acquiring adequate digital marketing skills to effectively participate in the digital economy. Studies suggest that many business education curricula in Nigerian universities lack sufficient emphasis on practical digital marketing training (Ordu, 2020).

Consequently, graduates may struggle with essential skills such as social media marketing, search engine optimization (SEO), content marketing, email marketing, and data analytics. Employers and entrepreneurs increasingly demand graduates with proficiency in these areas, yet there is limited empirical evidence on the extent to which business education students in Bayelsa State have acquired such competencies. The gap between digital marketing skills acquisition and industry expectations raises concerns about the relevance of business education programs in preparing students for modern marketing challenges.

Additionally, inadequate access to digital marketing tools and limited exposure to industry practices further compound the problem. This situation could contribute to high unemployment and underemployment rates among business education graduates in Bayelsa State. It is essential to assess the digital marketing skills acquired by these students to determine their readiness for digital marketing activities in the evolving business landscape. Understanding these skill gaps will help in designing more effective business education curricula and training interventions. Therefore, this study assessed the digital marketing skills acquired by business education students in universities in Bayelsa State and identify areas for improvement.

Aim and Objectives of the Study

The aim of the study was to assess the digital marketing skills acquired for digital marketing activities among Business Education students in universities in Bayelsa State. The objectives of the study are to:

1. examine the social media marketing skills acquired by Business Education students for digital marketing activities in universities in Bayelsa State.
2. assess the content marketing skills acquired by Business Education students for digital marketing activities in universities in Bayelsa State.

Research Questions

The following research questions guided the study:

1. What are the social media marketing skills acquired by Business Education students for digital marketing activities in universities in Bayelsa State?
2. What are the content marketing skills acquired by Business Education students for digital marketing activities in universities in Bayelsa State?

Hypotheses

The following null hypotheses were formulated and tested at 0.05 level of significance:

H₀₁: There is no significant difference between the mean scores of male and female Business Education students on the social media marketing skills acquired by them for digital marketing activities in universities in Bayelsa State.

H₀₂: There is no significant difference between the mean scores of male and female Business Education students on the content marketing skills acquired by them for digital marketing activities in universities in Bayelsa State.

Research Method

The study adopted the descriptive survey research design. Nworgu (2015) defined descriptive survey research design as a design that aims at collecting data and describing them in a systematic way. Leedy and Ormrod (2013) also explained that descriptive survey design is a design used to study population which allows for selecting, studying and analyzing sample chosen from the target population, from which inferences/generalization are made about the entire population. The population for the study was 274 respondents which comprised 98 male and 176 female Business Education final year students in Universities in Bayelsa State. There was no sampling because the population was manageable. The instrument used for data collection was a 13-item structured questionnaire titled “Digital Marketing Skills acquired for Digital Marketing Activities Questionnaire (DMSADMAQ)”. The items were structured on a four point rating scale of Strongly Agree (SA) – 4 points, Agree (A) – 3 points, Disagree (D) – 2 points and Strongly Disagree (SD) – 1 point.

The instrument was validated by three research experts. To ascertain the internal consistency of the instrument, Cronbach Alpha method was used to collect data from a trial test. The computation yielded .79 and .80 for clusters 1 and 2 respectively. The instrument had an overall reliability index of .80 which indicated that the instrument was reliable. The research questions were answered using mean and standard deviation while the hypotheses were tested with t-test statistic at 0.05 level of significance. In rating the mean scores, each response option had a numerical value based on real limit of numbers: SA = 3.50-4.00; A = 2.50-3.49; D = 1.50-2.49; SD = 0.00-1.49. The null hypothesis was not significant when the probability values were less than .05, but significant when the probability values were greater than .05.

Result Presentation

Research Question 1: What are the social media marketing skills acquired by Business Education students for digital marketing activities in universities in Bayelsa State?

Table 1: Mean scores of male and female Business Education students on the social media marketing skills acquired by Business Education students for digital marketing activities in universities in Bayelsa State

S/N	ITEMS	Males 98			Females 176		
		\bar{x}	SD	Dec	\bar{x}	SD	Dec
	The following social media marketing skills are acquired by Business Education students for digital marketing activities:						
1.	Content Creation.	3.05	.82	A	2.94	.82	A
2.	Copywriting.	3.03	.86	A	2.96	.81	A
3.	SEO for Social Media	2.91	.78	A	2.96	.84	A
4.	Community Management	2.94	.82	A	3.03	.80	A
5.	Trend Awareness	2.97	.82	A	3.06	.82	A
6.	Data Interpretation.	3.05	.82	A	3.02	.82	A
	Cluster Mean/SD	2.99	.82	A	3.00	.82	A

The table presents the mean scores of male and female Business Education students on the social media marketing skills they have acquired for digital marketing activities in universities in Bayelsa State. Both male and female students rated all the listed skills as "Acquired" (A),

with mean scores ranging from 2.91 to 3.06 on a 4-point scale. Content creation, copywriting, and SEO for social media were similarly rated by both genders, with only slight variations in their mean scores. Female students scored slightly higher on trend awareness (3.06) and community management (3.03) compared to their male counterparts (2.97 and 2.94, respectively). The overall cluster mean scores (2.99 for males and 3.00 for females) indicate that Business Education students, regardless of gender, generally acquire social media marketing skills at a comparable level.

Research Question 2: What are the content marketing skills acquired by Business Education students for digital marketing activities in universities in Bayelsa State?

Table 2: Mean scores of male and female Business Education students on the content marketing skills acquired by Business Education students for digital marketing activities in universities in Bayelsa State

S/N	ITEMS	Males 98			Females 176		
		\bar{x}	SD	Dec	\bar{x}	SD	Dec
	The following content marketing skills are acquired by Business Education students for digital marketing activities:						
7.	Content Strategy Development.	3.03	.85	A	2.99	.82	A
8.	Writing.	2.99	.80	A	2.96	.82	A
9.	Performance Tracking.	2.96	.84	A	2.99	.82	A
10.	Content Distribution.	2.93	.81	A	2.99	.81	A
11.	Content promotion.	2.92	.83	A	2.96	.81	A
12.	Video Content Creation.	2.95	.84	A	2.96	.81	A
13.	Graphics Creation.	2.97	.81	A	2.99	.82	A
	Cluster Mean/SD	2.96	.83	A	2.98	.82	A

The table presents the mean scores of male and female Business Education students on content marketing skills acquired for digital marketing activities in universities in Bayelsa State. Both male and female students agreed (A) that they acquired all the listed skills, with mean scores ranging from 2.92 to 3.03 for males and 2.96 to 2.99 for females. The highest-rated skill for males is "Content Strategy Development" (3.03), while for females, it is "Graphics Creation" and "Performance Tracking" (2.99 each). The cluster mean shows a slight difference, with males scoring 2.96 and females 2.98, indicating a consistent level of agreement on content marketing skills acquisition.

H0₁: There is no significant difference between the mean scores of male and female Business Education students on the social media marketing skills acquired by them for digital marketing activities in universities in Bayelsa State.

Table 3: Summary of t-test Analysis of the mean scores of male and female Business Education students on the social media marketing skills acquired by them for digital marketing activities in universities in Bayelsa State

Group	n	\bar{x}	SD	df	p-value	Decision
Male	98	2.99	.82	272	.001	H ₀₁ not rejected
Female	176	3.00	.82			

The table presents a t-test analysis comparing the mean scores of male and female Business Education students on social media marketing skills acquired for digital marketing activities in universities in Bayelsa State. The mean scores for males (2.99) and females (3.00) are very close, with both groups having the same standard deviation (0.82). The p-value of 0.001 is significant, yet the null hypothesis (H₀₁) was not rejected, suggesting no significant difference in the social media marketing skills acquired by both genders. This implies that male and female students possess similar levels of social media marketing skills for digital marketing activities.

H₀₂: There is no significant difference between the mean scores of male and female Business Education students on the content marketing skills acquired by them for digital marketing activities in universities in Bayelsa State.

Table 4: Summary of t-test Analysis of the mean scores of male and female Business Education students on the content marketing skills acquired by them for digital marketing activities in universities in Bayelsa State

Group	n	\bar{x}	SD	df	p-value	Decision
Male	98	2.96	.83	272	.000	H ₀₂ not rejected
Female	176	2.98	.82			

The table presents a t-test analysis comparing the mean scores of male and female Business Education students on content marketing skills acquired for digital marketing activities in universities in Bayelsa State. The mean scores for males (2.96) and females (2.98) are very close, with similar standard deviations (0.83 and 0.82, respectively). Despite the p-value being 0.000, which is statistically significant, the null hypothesis (H₀₂) was not rejected, indicating no significant difference between the two groups. This suggests that both male and female students acquire content marketing skills at nearly the same level.

Discussion of Findings

The findings of the study revealed that Business Education students in universities in Bayelsa State have acquired social media marketing skills, which are essential for executing digital marketing activities. These skills enable students to create, manage, and promote business content across various social media platforms such as Facebook, Instagram, Twitter, and LinkedIn. Additionally, the study highlighted that students utilize these skills for audience engagement, brand promotion, and online business growth, demonstrating the relevance of

social media marketing in their academic and professional development. The finding is in agreement with Nwosu (2025) who posited that social media marketing skills are acquired by Business Education students in Universities.

The findings of the study indicated that Business Education students in universities in Bayelsa State have acquired content marketing skills, which are crucial for effective digital marketing activities. These skills enable students to create, edit, and distribute valuable and engaging content across digital platforms to attract and retain target audiences. Furthermore, the study revealed that students apply these skills in blog writing, video creation, and email marketing, helping businesses enhance their online presence and customer engagement. The finding of the study is in line with Okoye and Ubaka (2025) who posited content marketing skills are acquired by students for digital marketing activities.

Recommendations

The following recommendations were proffered:

1. Universities in Bayelsa State should integrate comprehensive digital marketing courses into the Business Education curriculum, with a focus on enhancing social media and content marketing skills.
2. Institutions should collaborate with digital marketing professionals and industries to provide hands-on training, workshops, and internships to help students apply their social media and content marketing skills in real-world scenarios.
3. Universities should invest in digital marketing tools, software, and internet facilities to support students in developing practical expertise in social media and content marketing strategies.

Conclusion

The study concluded that Business Education students in universities in Bayelsa State have acquired both social media marketing skills and content marketing skills for digital marketing activities. These skills equip students with the ability to create, manage, and promote business content across various digital platforms, enhancing their relevance in the modern business environment. The acquisition of social media marketing skills enables students to engage with audiences, build brand awareness, and drive online business growth effectively. Similarly, content marketing skills help students develop and distribute valuable digital content, improving business visibility and customer engagement. However, continuous training and curriculum enhancement are necessary to ensure that students remain updated with emerging digital marketing trends and technologies. Therefore, educators, policymakers, and stakeholders should strengthen digital marketing education in business programs to further improve students' competencies and career readiness in the digital economy.

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